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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG MEDICAL
SALES REPRESENTATIVES WORKING IN KARACHI CITY,
PAKISTAN**

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Abstract:**Objective:**

The objective of this study was to assess the level of job satisfaction among medical sales representatives working in Karachi city, Pakistan.

Methods:

This was a cross-sectional, survey based study. The study was conducted among medical representative working in different pharmaceutical corporations of Karachi city, Pakistan. A total of 519 respondents were considered in this study. The modified Likert Scale of (agreeability) questionnaire containing 20 questions was used for data collection. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data collection with level of significance set at < 0.05. SPSS 21 was used for data analysis.

Results:

550 questionnaires were distributed out of which 519 questioners were received. Male respondents were 486 (93.6%) and 268 (51.6%) had B.Sc. level of education. 446 (86%) were employed in a local company. Job satisfaction was rated as satisfactory among medical representative with a special focus on salary and promotion. Lack of benefits and rewards, workload and extraordinary strictness of rules were identified as factors leading to dissatisfaction. Age, education, gender, company, position and experience were significantly associated with the study questions.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that the medical representatives were encountered by several tasks in their duty. A number of issues disturb their capability to complete their responsibilities. Major concerns were related to rewards and deficiencies of benefits, lack of promotion were identified as factors leading to dissatisfaction. In summary, medical representatives were satisfied with their current job status.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, medical representatives, pharmaceutical companies, Karachi, Pakistan

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INTRODUCTION:

Job satisfaction is a composite function of a number of variables [1]. Someone may possibly be satisfied by one and additional features of his/her profession however at the similar time may be hopeless by additional belongings associated to their job for example, a medical representative might be satisfied with his designation but may not be satisfied with his/her income level [1]. Job satisfaction has been deliberated widely in expressions of psychology and sociology [2-10]. In layman languages it is defined as the contentment level of a single consumer with his/her job [3]. Locke states that the main cause for progress lack in consideration of the job satisfaction conception and disappointment is 'implied conception of casualty' acknowledged through maximum psychologist [2].

Job satisfaction is a precise significant characteristic dignified by organizations commonly by means of mark scale [3, 4, 10]. Worldwide scores for job satisfaction are additional wide-ranging job satisfaction measurements than the yes/no single-item worldwide query [4, 10].

The respondent is working in a company facing many problems such as; sufficient work related materials, realistic payment, medical designation, leave facility, attitude of supervisor, rewards for work performance, welfare, job security, personal development, job satisfaction and other various choices are the variables taken into attention for this study [10]. Most of the investigated variables clues to the defendant working in a pharmaceutical company. (Kabir & Parvin examined the pharmaceutical sector employee job satisfaction in Bangladesh by dissimilar variables such as at work condition, promotion and pay, relation by work colleagues, fairness and manager and estimated that the whole satisfaction level amongst pharmaceutical workforces as (not excessively satisfied or excessively unsatisfied) [11]. Maximum of the features were selected in the research centered on earlier researches [12], job satisfaction was projected by means of prize and price standards of the job in languages of investment replicas [10]. Organizational climate effects such as attitude of supervisor's inspiration job satisfaction and performance as fine [12]. Work values have liberated possessions on job satisfaction [13]. Six work scales used by Kalleberg i.e., convenience, intrinsic, career opportunities, financial, relations with co-workers and work values and resource competence to inspect the association among job satisfaction [13].

Within this context, there are nearly 5000 pharmaceutical corporations listed in Pakistan by the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan

[14]. Between these listed corporations, 90% are private limited, 6% of them are single participant and 4% listed as non-profit associations, public unlisted, foreign companies and trade organizations [14]. However, there is not a single study that evaluates job satisfaction among medical representatives. Therefore, the current study is aimed to assess the level of job satisfaction among medical representatives working in Karachi city, Pakistan.

METHODS:**Study design and settings**

This was a questionnaire based, cross-sectional survey. The study was conducted among medical representatives working in different pharmaceutical corporations of Karachi city, Pakistan.

Sample size and study tool

A total of 519 respondents were targeted by non-probability convenience sampling method. A Likert Scale containing 20 questions on job satisfaction was constructed. The objective of the study was clarified to participants and written consent was taken.

Data collection procedure

550 questionnaires were distributed to medical representatives attending the private and public hospitals, GP's Clinics and Primary health care Initiatives (PPHI). 530 questionnaires were returned back, out of which 11 questionnaires were excluded. The data was collected for the period of 6 months. Medical representatives who decided to participate in the research were enquired to fill the questionnaire on the spot. However, questionnaires were left with the respondents and were collected after a maximum of four working days.

Ethical approval

Institutional Ethical Committee, Faculty of Pharmacy and Health Sciences, University of Balochistan approved the study. Additionally, written consent from the participants was also taken.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS v 20 was used for data collection and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. $P < 0.05$ was observed as significant value.

RESULTS:**Demographic characteristics**

550 questionnaires and 519 were received with a response rate of 94.3%. 217 (41.8%) belonged to the age group of 28-37 years while males dominated the cohort 486 (93.6%). 268 (51.6%) had B.Sc. level of education while 446 (86%) were working in a national pharmaceutical firm. 366 (70.5%) were working as sales representatives followed by 92 (17.7%) of managers as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of study respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-27	226	43.5
28-37	217	41.8
38-47	65	12.5
> 47	11	2.1
Gender		
Male	486	93.6
Female	33	6.4
Educational level		
Intermediate	43	8.3
B.Sc	268	51.6
BPharm/PharmD	66	12.7
M.Sc	76	14.6
Others	66	12.7
Type of Company		
Multinational	73	14.0
National	446	86.0
Position		
Medical representative	366	70.5
Manager	92	17.7
Sales manager	61	11.8
Experience		
< 5 years	322	62.0
5-10 years	134	25.8
> 10 years	63	12.1

Perception of medical representative about their job satisfaction

20 questions were used to assess job satisfaction as shown in table 2. 325 (62.6%) of the respondents agreed that they are being paid a fair amount for the work they do. Mix responses were shown on promotion and received benefits as almost 30% of the respondents agreed, disagreed or stayed neutral to the statement.

326 (62.8%) of the respondents appreciated that whenever they do a good job, they receive the

recognition for it. However, 50% reported that many rules and procedures makes job difficult. Almost 50% also agreed that the benefits they receive were as good as other organizations offer but because of the incompetence of people they work with, makes their job difficult. 55% liked the things they do at work however were not agreed with the benefit package. Regarding the workload, almost 55% agreed to the statement that the workload is massive but even then they felt a sense of pride in doing their job. 337 (64.9%) were satisfied with their job.

Table 2: Perception of medical representative about job satisfaction

Items in Questionnaire	Agree		Neutral		Disagree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do	325	62.6	146	28.1	48	0.3
There is really too little chance for promotion on my job	197	38.0	157	30.3	165	31.9
I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive	206	39.7	147	28.3	166	32.0
When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive	326	62.8	170	32.8	23	4.4
Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult	261	50.3	158	30.4	100	19.3
Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted	255	49.1	178	34.3	86	16.5
The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer	246	47.4	160	30.8	113	21.8
I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with	256	49.3	191	36.8	72	13.9
I like doing the things I do at work	288	55.5	123	23.7	108	20.7
The goals of this organization are not clear to me	149	28.7	120	23.1	250	48.1
I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me	204	39.3	151	29.1	164	31.5
The benefit package we have is equitable	279	53.8	160	30.8	78	15.0
There are few rewards for those who work here	251	48.4	185	35.6	83	16.0
I to do have too much at work	283	54.5	174	33.5	60	11.6
I enjoy my coworkers	271	52.2	216	41.6	32	6.2
I feel a sense of pride in doing my job	289	55.7	139	26.8	91	17.5
There are benefits we do not have which we should have	263	50.7	122	23.5	134	25.7
I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be	248	47.8	153	29.5	118	22.7
My job is enjoyable	329	63.4	137	26.4	53	10.2
I am satisfied with my job	337	64.9	167	32.2	15	2.9

The significance difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed for age, education, gender, company, position and experience by applying the Kruskal Wallis and Man Whitney test as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Association among study variables and survey items

Items in Questionnaire	P-Value					
	Age*	Education*	Gender**	Company**	Position*	Experience*
I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do	0.611	0.000	0.060	0.926	0.141	0.952
There is really too little chance for promotion on my job	0.400	0.244	0.239	0.085	0.169	0.843
I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive	0.006	0.073	0.131	0.852	0.003	0.663
When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive	0.041	0.650	0.652	0.121	0.592	0.950
Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult	0.027	0.174	0.185	0.071	0.301	0.005
Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted	0.128	0.878	0.131	0.472	0.018	0.853
The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer	0.025	0.936	0.630	0.198	0.061	0.303
I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with	0.006	0.630	0.691	0.055	0.223	0.589
I like doing the things I do at work	0.002	0.090	0.741	0.051	0.527	0.948
The goals of this organization are not clear to me	0.124	0.099	0.801	0.630	0.195	0.890
I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me	0.015	0.270	0.170	0.501	0.613	0.018
The benefit package we have is equitable	0.529	0.235	0.923	0.660	0.004	0.053
There are few rewards for those who work here	0.001	0.023	0.557	0.357	0.422	0.003
I have too much to do at work	0.049	0.949	0.435	0.893	0.258	0.579
I enjoy my coworkers	0.000	0.436	0.794	0.128	0.034	0.110
I feel a sense of pride in doing my job	0.000	0.693	0.635	0.465	0.045	0.066
There are benefits we do not have which we should have	0.289	0.754	0.111	0.486	0.060	0.048
I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be	0.714	0.001	0.058	0.218	0.475	0.166
My job is enjoyable	0.001	0.016	0.421	0.184	0.170	0.012
I am satisfied with my job	0.657	0.039	0.976	0.029	0.072	0.034

*Kruskall Wallis test, Man Whitney test

DISCUSSION:

The most of medical representatives were agree to the statements provided in the questionnaire. Hence, a positive attitude was observed from most of the medical representatives when questioned about the job satisfaction. The 337 (64.9%) of medical representative were agree to the statement “I am satisfied with my job” and 167 (32.2%) of medical representatives were neutral to the statement and only 15 (2.9%) disagreed with the statement. While the study performed by Arafat in 2015 reported opposite findings [10]. The difference can be because of the metropolitan city where because of intense pressure pharmaceutical companies are forced to provide the same perks.

The job satisfaction factors especially rewards are always important [10] but in the present study few rewards were identified by 251(48.4%) of the respondents. This is a key finding and pharmaceutical companies should take notice of this lacking as soon as possible to avoid retention of employees.

The statement about “realistic payment” revealed that 325 (62.6%) of the respondents believed that they are paid fairly and most of the medical representatives were observed satisfied about receiving their pay in the present study which is opposite to a study reported in Pakistan and needs further investigation [10].

In this research, we observed that various factors such as salary benefit, good performance and promotion lead to job satisfaction. Therefore, the results of this study may assist forthcoming juniors who are attracted in medical representative fields to advance their profession. This can also deliver standard for pharmaceutical personnel in making an enhanced atmosphere and work standard for their medical personnel. Additionally, the analyzed aspects originate can also help employee and employer to mutually asses their job shortcomings and achievement which may lead to profits for the both parties.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the medical representatives were encountered by several tasks in their duty. A number of issues disturb their capability to complete their responsibilities. Major concerns were related to rewards and deficiencies of benefits, lack of promotion were identified as factors leading to dissatisfaction. In summary, medical representatives were satisfied with their current job status. Companies must emphasis on aspects leading to well job satisfaction between their staffs if they are thoughtful of increasing and attractive their respected pharmaceutical corporation.

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